

to WSD was 71.6, 17.6, and 10.9.

The results explain rolling and unrolling of rice leaves at high SMT. Rice

leaves roll severely at noon because of high internal moisture stress caused by bright sunshine. In the morning and in

the afternoon they remain open because of lower WSD caused by lower solar radiation. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Success with old rice seedlings

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In parts of North India, temperature is low during ripening of rice and young seedlings transplanted late yield low. The transplanting begins and continues at different ages depending upon the farmers' resources (irrigation, labor, machinery, etc.). An experiment was conducted to assess the yield variation that results from transplanting seedlings at different ages and to explore the possibility of averting yield reduction through the use of seedlings from sparsely seeded puddled nurseries (25 and 50 g seed/m² vs the 100-g/m² recommended practice). The rice variety was Jaya. A randomized block design with 3 replications was used. The nursery was sown on 9 June 1976, seedlings were transplanted at 25, 35, 45, and 55 days old at 20 × 15-cm spacing. Seedlings were uprooted with the Khurpi so that there was minimum injury to the seedlings, particularly the old ones. Care was also exercised to ensure that all the shoots of the old seedlings were included when transplanted at 2 seedlings/hill. Thus, 2, 3, 4.5, and 5.5 shoots/hill were transplanted at 25, 35, 45, and 55 days age, respectively. Nitrogen fertilizer was applied to the nursery at 100, 125, 150, and 175 kg N/ha for the different ages. In the main field, the crop was fertilized with 120 kg N/ha.

The yield reductions caused by transplanting old seedlings were small and nonsignificant (Table 1). The yield was 11% lower in 55-day-old seedlings than in 25-day-old. Ripening occurred during 16-27 October (Table 2) and the crop was exposed to a mean maximum air temperature of 31.5°-32.2°C and to a

Table 1. Grain yield of rice variety Jaya as influenced by seedling age and seeding rate in nursery, 1976.

Seedling age (days)	Grain yield (t/ha) at seeding rate of			Mean
	25 g/m ²	50 g/m ²	100 g/m ²	
25	8.00	8.25	7.82	8.02
35	7.67	7.74	7.87	7.76
45	7.68	7.54	6.99	7.40
55	7.34	7.26	6.85	7.15
Mean	7.67	7.70	7.38	

Treatment	S.Em. 1	C.D. 5%
Seedling age	181	Nonsignificant
Seed rate	157	Nonsignificant
Interaction	315	Nonsignificant
C.V. %	7.2	

minimum temperature of 17.3°-15.2°C (cold), respectively. Aged seedlings (45 and 55 days) experienced more cool weather than the young seedlings (25 and 35 days). Using well-grown seed-

Survey of farmers' rainfed and irrigated cropping patterns in Bangladesh

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A survey of the cropping patterns followed by farmers in Bangladesh was conducted by BRRI and the Directorate of Agriculture (Extension and Management), Government of the Peoples' Republic of Bangladesh, to prepare inventories of the existing cropping patterns under rainfed and irrigated conditions. A questionnaire was sent to the Extension Officer/ Agriculture Officer of each *thana* (5th-level administrative unit) of the country. A total of 186 *thana* responded to the survey.

In the rainfed areas, the cropping

Table 2. Date of maturity of rice variety Jaya as influenced by seedling age and seeding rate in nursery, 1976.

Seedling age (days)	Date of maturity when Jaya was seeded at		
	25 g/m ²	50 g/m ²	100 g/m ²
25	16Oct	16 Oct	18 Oct
35	21 Oct	22 Oct	23 Oct
45	22 Oct	24Oct	26 Oct
55	24Oct	26 Oct	27 Oct

lings from sparse nurseries (25 g seed/m²) was 7.3% more advantageous than using seedlings from dense nurseries (100 g seed/m²). Thus, reasonably high yields can be obtained from 55-day-old seedlings, with slight reduction in yield, provided the seedlings are well managed and uprooted with the least injury and 5-6 well-developed shoots are transplanted in each hill. ■

intensity was 100-300%. The most common cropping pattern reported by 100 *thana* was jute - transplanted aman rice (t. aman) - rabi crops (winter crops: oilseeds, potato, wheat, tobacco). The next most common pattern reported by 87 *thana* was aus rice (mainly a direct-seeded crop) - t. aman rice - rabi crops (wheat, *panicum* sp., oilseeds, pulses, spices). Among the double-cropping patterns reported were jute - rabi crops (63 *thana*), jute - t. aman rice (30 *thana*), and aus rice - t. aman rice (18 *thana*). Single cropping of aus rice, t. aman rice, B. aman (deepwater) rice, potato, oilseeds, vegetables, and spices was also reported for the rainfed areas.

The survey revealed that in the irrigated areas, farmers practiced single, double, and triple cropping. Aus rice - t. aman rice - rabi crops (wheat, potato, oilseeds, winter vegetables, tobacco, etc.) was the most common cropping pattern (178 *thana*), followed by the aus rice - t. aman rice - boro rice pattern (108

thana). Among the double-cropping patterns, boro rice - t. aman rice and aus rice - t. aman rice were the most common patterns, each reported by 10% of the sample thana. The next most common patterns were aus rice - boro rice and aus rice - rabi crops. Single cropping of rice (mostly boro), wheat,

tobacco, vegetables, and spices, was also reported for the irrigated areas. Jute crop was confined to the rainfed areas.

Single cropping patterns were reported by about 40% thana under rainfed conditions and 18% under irrigated conditions. Also more thana practiced double-cropping patterns in the

rainfed conditions (44%) than in the irrigated (28%). On the other hand, more thana (78%) reported triple-cropping patterns under irrigated conditions than under the rainfed (60%).

These results indicate that the opportunity exists for crop intensification in Bangladesh. ■

Announcements

Honors for E. P. Alyoshin

The USSR's Order of People's Friendship was awarded to Dr. E. P. Alyoshin in February 1981. Dr. Alyoshin is a corresponding member of the USSR Agricultural Academy and director of the All-Union Rice Research Institute. The award, made through an edict from the USSR Supreme Soviet Presidium, acknowledged Dr. Alyoshin's role in the scientific support of the production of 1 million tons of rice in the Krasnodar territory in 1980. ■

E. P. Alyoshin, recipient of the USSR's Order of People's Friendship.

ICAR award to Dr. R. C. Chaudhary

The Indian Council of Agricultural Research awarded the *Kheti Purashkar* to Dr. R. C. Chaudhary, chief scientist, rice, Bihar. The award is given for popular scientific publications in agriculture, which convey to readers the significance of recent scientific advances to improve biological productivity. It carries a cash prize and a citation. Dr. Chaudhary's award acknowledged the release and promotion of the rice variety Prasad in India. Prasad is a reselection from the introduced IRRI line IR1561-216-6. Dr. Chaudhary is presently a senior post-doctoral fellow in the IRRI plant breeding department. ■

Sterling Wortman dies at 58

Dr. Sterling Wortman died of cancer 26 May 1981 in Greenwich, Connecticut, USA. He was 58 years old. Wortman was the founder of the International Agricultural Development Service (IADS) and served as its president from 1975 to 1979.

Dr. Wortman joined the Rockefeller

Foundation in 1950 as a maize breeder in the foundation's Mexican agricultural program. In 1955 he went to the Pineapple Research Institute in Hawaii.

When the International Rice Research Institute was launched in 1960, he rejoined the Rockefeller Foundation and, on assignment, served IRRI until 1964 as assistant director and associate director. He then became director

of the Pineapple Research Institute. In 1966 he was appointed director of agricultural sciences for the Rockefeller Foundation. He became vice president of the foundation in 1970.

When IADS was founded in 1975 he served as both president of IADS and vice president of the Rockefeller Foundation. ■

International training on Seed Technology for Vegetable Crops

The fourth International Course on Seed Technology for Vegetable Crops will be held 1 September - 17 November 1982 (closing date for applications: 1 April 1982). The course, organized by the University of the Philippines at Los

Baños (UPLB) in cooperation with the International Agricultural Centre at Wageningen, the Netherlands, will be held at UPLB.

The course is primarily for individuals whose agricultural education background is equivalent to a BS and whose work involves the development of vegetable seed. It will concentrate on

vegetable crops grown in the Asian and Pacific region. Brochures, including application forms, will be sent to various institutes and entities in the region.

For more information, write to: Project Directorate, International Programme on Seed Technology, P. O. Box 430, College, Laguna 3720, Philippines. ■